

Project Title	UKRI transforming food systems- Study three: feast for the eyes:
Status	Approved
Email	E.Swan@sussex.ac.uk
Phone No.	
Applicant Status	Staff (Senior Lecturer in Human Resources and Organisational Behaviour)
Department	Management
Project Start Date	06-Dec-2021
Project End Date	31-Dec-2023
External Funding in place	Yes
External Collaborators	Yes
Funder/Project Title	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council - Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvant
Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council
Project Description	<p>"Feast for the Eyes': Using Photography for Understanding People's understandings of and relationship to food is a research study that is part of the broader £6M UKRI-funded research programme 'Co-production of healthy, sustsinable food systems for disadvantaged communities'.</p> <p>This study is focused on an in-depth qualitative study of a small sample of residents of St Georges Estate in Shadwell, London. The study will involve different research activities, including attending 8 photography workshops, semi-structured interviews, focus groups and an exhibition. The aim is to use photography as a way for participants to share their food lives, memories, celebrations and difficulties. Participants will have control over what photographs they take, share and what they discuss.</p> <p>This research study is part of the bigger UKRI-funded project. Dr Katerina Psarikidou and Dr Elaine Swan are the project research investigators based at the University of Sussex. Based on the principles of research co-production, the project is envisioned to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse communities with choice and agency over the food they consume, the chains through which they access their food, and the policy frameworks that are needed to support the vision of a more inclusive and socio-environmentally just agri-food system for all.</p>

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/ES483/4)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	No
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	Yes
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	Yes
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	Yes
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	
A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.	

Ethical Review Form Section C (ER/ES483/4)	
Question	Response
>> Risk Checklist - Participants	
C1. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete Section C24a below	No
C2. Are alcoholic drinks, drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) to be administered to the study participants?	No
C3. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to participants in this research?	There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices, food poverty, food relations and understandings. The lead researcher has received training in counselling skills and is aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants and for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing photography based research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researchers will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. The team will have a list of contacts that may be able to provide help in relation to emergency food aid and possible disordered eating.
C4. Does the project involve working with any substances and/or equipment which may be considered hazardous? (Please refer to the University's Control of Hazardous Substances Policy http://www.sussex.ac.uk/hso/policies).	No
C5. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially have an emotionally disturbing impact on the researcher(s)?	Yes

<p>C5a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to help the researcher(s) to manage this.</p>	<p>The researchers will be given support within the team through debriefing and discussion. The researchers are experienced in researching the topics and with potential participants.</p>
<p>C6. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially expose the researcher(s) to threats of physical violence and / or verbal abuse?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>C6a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to mitigate this.</p>	
<p>C7. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C7a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? (All research requiring overseas travel will require the submission of a fully completed OTTSRA form). In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment.</p>	<p>The fieldwork will take place at St Georges Estate in one of the rooms. Some will take place in the grounds of the estate and local markets. The fieldwork will be undertaken during usual work hours in spaces where there are other adults. Most of the fieldwork will take place in locations with which the lead researcher is relatively familiar</p>
<p>C8. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>C8a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?</p>	
<p>C9. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to the researcher(s) in this research?</p>	<p>Nothing more than the usual stresses of undertaking academic research on such topics as discussed in C5a</p>
<p>>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)</p>	

C10. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?

Eight adult participants who are residents of St Georges Estate, Shadwell. They will be selected on the basis of their interest in the photography course and research project and a first come, first served basis. If more people want to do the course/research, we can run more events.

C11. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?

They will recruited via an information leaflet distributed through their letterboxes by a paid distributor and inclusion in the December estate newsletter. Agreement has been obtained from the estate manager about the process. The leaflet and newsletter will briefly describe the photography course and the research but will link to a website with more detailed information. The leaflet, newsletter and website will include Elaine Swan's email account for people to register. We will also have a project page on Facebook to promote recruitment with a UoS email for people to contact. At the start of the first workshop, we will brief on the ethical process, provide information sheets and informed consent forms. The participants will have the opportunity to raise any questions about the project. The researchers will explain informed consent and go through the information sheet with individuals in person.

<p>C12. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording etc.?</p>	<p>We plan to use interviews, focus group, participant observation and photographic analysis. The researchers will also take field notes and observations that will form part of the analysis. The participants will be given food related photographic assignments as part of each workshop. For example, these will include taking photographs in their homes, on the estate, in the community orchard and allotments, a local market, and of everyday food, celebratory foods, traditional foods.</p>
<p>C13. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?</p>	<p>The research will be carried out in a semi public venue on St Georges Estate, in its semi public grounds and local public environs.</p>
<p>>> Ethical Considerations (Please provide full details)</p>	

C14. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.

Participants will be asked to discuss their relationship to food using photographic research methods, interviews and focus groups. There is possibility these could raise some anxiety or distress. We will take steps to explain the study to the participants. They will have full control too over whether they exhibit their photographs.

Participants will be able to withdraw at any point within the workshop themselves, without having to provide any explanation. They may request withdrawal of their data by 14th July 2022 which is two weeks after the end of the data collection and the start of our data analysis.

<p>C15. INFORMED CONSENT: Please describe the process you will use to ensure your participants are freely giving fully informed consent to participate. This will usually include the provision of an Information Sheet and will normally require a Consent Form unless there is justification for not doing so. (Please state this clearly).</p>	<p>We will provide an information sheet and consent form and talk these through at the first workshop. The information provided will consist of an explicit invitation to participate in the study, the purpose of the study, and the way in which possible participants will be asked to engage. Photographs taken by participants that they consent to share will be uploaded to a 'burner phone' in Elaine Swan's name or to her university email. Participants will make further decisions about which of their photographs they wish to exhibit in the final exhibition of photographs, taken account of our guidelines on images of people.</p>
<p>C16. RIGHT OF WITHDRAWAL: Participants should be able to withdraw from the research at any time. Participants should also be able to withdraw their data if it is linked to them and should be told when this will no longer be possible (e.g. once it has been included in the final report). Please describe the exact arrangements for withdrawal from participation and withdrawal of data for your study.</p>	<p>Participants will be able to withdraw at any point within the workshop themselves, without having to provide any explanation. They may request withdrawal of their data by 14th July 2022 which is two weeks after the end of the data collection and the start of our data analysis. This information will form part of the information sheet and discussion.</p>

C17. OTHER ETHICAL ISSUES: If you answered YES to anything in A.1 above (participants who are potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position) you must specifically address this here. Please also consider whether there are other ethical issues you should be covering here. Please also refer to the professional code of conduct you intend to follow in your research.

As the research is focused upon peoples' relationships with and understandings of food, it is possible that the photographs and discussions themselves might raise topics that are potentially emotionally difficult or sensitive for the participants. The lead researchers and photographer have experience of working and researching within socially deprived environments and they are particularly sensitive to the potential vulnerabilities of participants. Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and all researchers have experience of studying food lives and food poverty issues and are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, and for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing photographic research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researchers will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. As reflexivity is of the utmost importance throughout the research process, the researchers will maintain a research diary where they explore ethical issues as they arise and which will serve as a means for them to constantly reflect upon the research process and to share these reflections

with colleagues in the
research team.

>> Data Protection, Confidentiality, and Records Management	
C18. DPA: Will you ensure that the processing of personal information related to the study will be in full compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR)? Please give full details under C19a. (http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa)	Yes
C18a. If you are processing any personal information outside of the European Economic Area (EEA) you must explain how compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR) will be ensured. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa/transfersoutsideeea	
C19. CONFIDENTIALITY: Will you take steps to ensure the confidentiality of personal information? Please explain how any identifiable personal records and research data will be managed and stored whilst ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this in C19a and or C20 below.	Yes

C19a. DATA MANAGEMENT: Please provide details of any anonymisation procedures and of physical and technical security measures (including secure storage) of identifiable personal and research data here. Indicate how these will be employed in the collection, analysis and research output and dissemination stages.

The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities although the limitations of this will be discussed with them given the workshop format and the exhibition. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using Sussex Box. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to Box, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on Box will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team.

<p>C20. CONSENT: If personal information related to this study will be retained and shared (i.e. in outputs) in a form that is not fully anonymised (separated from information that can identify the participant) please outline how participants will be made aware of this (including any limitations) and indicate their consent.</p>	<p>Participants will need to consent to their photographs and recordings of the workshops being shared. This will be done at the start of the course and the preparation for the exhibition via the information sheet and a verbal briefing from the researchers.</p>
<p>C21. Will the Principal Investigator take full responsibility during the study, for ensuring appropriate storage and security of information (including research data, consent forms and administrative records) and, where appropriate, will the necessary arrangements be made in order to process copyright material lawfully?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C21a. If you answered "No" to the above question, please give further details of how data and records will be managed:</p>	
<p>C22. Who will have access to personal information and data relating to this study?</p>	<p>The lead researcher ie Elaine Swan will have responsibility for data and records management. The research fellow and project manager will have access to personal information and data.</p>

<p>C23. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN: AFTER the study: State how long study information including research data, consent forms and personal identification will be retained, in what format(s) and where the information will be kept.</p> <p>http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/recordsmanagementguidance</p>	<p>The data will be deposited in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) Figshare, where it will be preserved for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016) and to allow for maximum project exposure and impact. Participants will be notified in the participant information that their data will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR requirements and will only be presented anonymously.</p>
<p>>> Other Ethical Clearances and Permissions</p>	
<p>C24. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>C24a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).</p>	

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Feast for the eyes: Using photography to explore peoples' understandings of and relationships with food

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU, Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

Please tick box

	YES	NO
• I consent to engaging in photography workshops, interviews and focus group with the researcher.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree to allowing the photography workshops to be observed, photographed and audio-recorded.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree to allowing the interviews/workshops to be conducted and audio-recorded via the University of Sussex Zoom, and being stored in the University of Sussex storing systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I understand that if I consent to participate in the workshop I will be photographed, and audio-recorded.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• If I am participating in the workshop/focus group, I understand that any information disclosed within the workshop/meeting remains confidential to the group, and I will not discuss the workshop with or in front of anyone who was not involved unless I have the relevant person's permission.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• However, I understand that confidentiality cannot always be guaranteed for information which I might disclose in the focus groups/workshops.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with Data Protection legislation .	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name:

Signature:

Date:

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

STUDY TITLE

'Feast for the eyes": Using photography to explore peoples' understandings of and relationships with food.

INVITATION

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about peoples' understanding of food within their local communities.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you are an adult resident of the St. Georges Estate in the London Borough of Tower Hamlets. We are interested in people's understandings of food and we think you will have ideas and experiences which we think are important for researchers and policy makers to understand.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. You may request withdrawal of your data by 14th July 2022 which is two weeks after the end of the data collection and the start of our data analysis. You will have the final say on whether you share your photographic images in the workshop, with the researchers and in the exhibition.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You're invited to participate in an 8 week photographic course with 1.5 hour workshops. You will be asked to take photographs each week, talk about your experiences of taking the photographs and listen to other people's experiences. During the workshop you will learn skills in photography. With your consent, the discussion will be audio recorded and researchers will take notes on what you say and do. We will invite you to take part in a 1 hour interview or focus group once the workshops have finished. With your consent, we will exhibit a selection of your photographs.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress that can be generated by discussing food will be kept to the minimum through the activities chosen, and the experience of the researchers and photographer. Dr Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and the researchers and photographer are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, and for the wellbeing of everyone involved. By employing photographic research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study you are helping to expand knowledge on things that impact you in your life. Specifically, this research aims to understand how you feel about the food you eat, and how your understanding of food changes through taking photographs and learning from other people on the course.

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Taking part in this project will also mean you get the opportunity to engage creatively with other people using photography and you will develop skills in photography. You will also be invited to submit your photographs to an exhibition and a magazine. We aim to share your ideas and experiences with policy makers.

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential and private. Confidentiality and privacy will be ensured by us adhering to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. After the interview/workshop, only the researchers will have access to your input. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g. your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcripts produced by the transcriber. We will store your data separate from the consent form to de-identify you.

We cannot guarantee anonymity and because of the nature of the workshops and the photographs. But all participants in workshops are requested to consent to keep all information disclosed within the workshops confidential, and not discuss the workshop with or in front of anyone who was not involved unless they have the relevant person's permission. Participants should note that personal data will be retained for the duration of the project which will be February 2025 and research data for ten years starting from January 2022. This research project may involve the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: <https://explore.zoom.us/en/privacy/>.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form and making yourself available for the workshops.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform a number of academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 4 year period, with data retained for the length of that period. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes (e.g. from the interview/focus group with you), so that although we will use your exact words, we will do our best to ensure you cannot be identified in the publications, although we cannot guarantee this.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Management Department and Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a larger UKRI research study entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been improved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is [XX/XXXX/X].

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. Any concerns regarding the way in which the study has been conducted should be directed toward [X] (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project) by emailing [X].

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

THANK-YOU

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.

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[DATE]

Indicative questions for interviews/focus group

- What words would you use to describe your experience of the photo workshops?
- What do you feel you learned about food?
- What did you learn about photography?
- What did you learn from the other participants about their food lives?
- What did you learn from other participants about photography?
- What did you find most surprising to learn about your relationship to food through taking photographs?
- How do you think your understanding or feelings about food shifted during the workshop?
- Which was the photo you found easiest to take and why?
- Which was the most difficult and why?
- Which photos would you like to exhibit and why?
- Were there photos you would have liked to have taken but couldn't? What were these?
- How do you think your perceptions change about where you live and shop through taking photographs?
- Has your view of your neighbours changed as a result of doing the course?
- What do you think other people could learn about your food life from these photos?
- Do you think you will continue to take photos?

Consent to be photographed

Study title:

'Feast for the eyes": Using photography to explore peoples' understandings of and relationships with food.

Name of Researchers and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, Dr Elaine Swan and UKRI Research Fellow, Dr Jesse Hsu (Business School)

Date:

I agree to the taking of my portrait by photographer X on DATE

.....atand hereby give all consents necessary for the reproduction of any of the resulting photographs and agree to the exhibition, transmission, broadcast and exploitation thereof without time limit throughout the universe by all means and media (whether now known or hereafter invented) without liability or acknowledgement to me. I acknowledge that their agents, associates or assigns can use and authorize the use of the photograph(s) however they see fit. I declare I am over 18 years of age.

Yours Faithfully

Name:

Contact email:

Elaine Swan – Feast for the Eyes ethics submission

Please consider the points made below, and resubmit your application to the committee.

1 - Within your resubmission please can you clarify what will be filmed and the photographs will consist of. You should also consider that participants may be identifiable even if they are not depicted in the images, for example a plate of food on a dinner table could lead to identification. This is not an issue provided that you remove sections and text within your participant-facing documents that state that anonymity will be provided.

Response – I have removed the sections and text within our participant-facing documents that state that anonymity will be provided. I have added extra information about what the photographs are likely to consist of below.

I have rethought the necessity of filming and taken this out as we won't be filming. It doesn't add much to our design.

The exact nature of the photographs will be developed with the photographer the participants. They will be themed for each workshop and themes are likely to be topics such as celebratory foods, everyday foods, shopping for food, foodwork. These may consist of photographs of ingredients, meals, kitchens, people eating, markets, allotments. Given that participants may want to photograph people as part of their food photographs, I have now included a photography portrait consent form using the template form the University's ethics webpage.

2 - Please amend your response to Section A3 to 'no' and state why in Section A10.

Response – I have amended this to no. My reasons for A10 which I can't add to the system:

I have answered No to A3 as we cannot guarantee complete anonymity to participants as they will be working together as a group for 8 weeks and their identity could be identified through their photographs and data from the workshops. We have made this clear in the information and consent sheets.

3 - In relation to Section C14 please can you state a specific date/time by which participants will no longer be able to withdraw from the research. You have detailed this in Section C16 but should also state this in Section C14 and also in the Participant Information Sheet

Response – I have added a specified date/time in C14 and on the Participant Information Sheet and revised C16 to make it consistent

4 - In relation to Section C19a - Please note that Box should not be used to store confidential project data such as consent forms. It is fine to use the BOX to manage anonymized data or data that participants have consented to share. All other research data should be stored within your UoS OneDrive

Response – I have changed the Section C19a, and information sheet accordingly and advised the research team

5 - Within Section C20 please can you provide some more information that clarifies that participants will need to consent to having their 'data' shared e.g., photographs, recordings of the workshops etc.

Response – I have added information to this effect

6 - Within the Consent Form please amend the statement "I understand that any information that is provided is confidential, and that no information that is disclosed will lead to the identification of any individual in future reports and publications, either by the researcher or by any other party." so that it states that participants who are consenting to having the workshops will be photographed / filmed / audio-recorded.

Response – I have amended the consent form accordingly

7 - Within the Consent Form please amend the statement "I agree to being informed about follow-up research activities and participate, should I be available." so that it instead reads 'I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research'

Response – I have amended the consent form accordingly

8 - You may wish to state in the Participant Information Sheet that the research activity will be conducted in English and if this is a requirement to taking part.

Response – I have added a sentence to this effect.

Please include a PDF with your resubmission that details how you have addressed the above points.

DONE

Thanks, Elaine

Certificate of Approval

Reference Number	ER/ES483/4
Title Of Project	UKRI transforming food systems- Study three: feast for the eyes:
Principal Investigator (PI):	Elaine Swan
Student	N/A
Collaborators	
Duration Of Approval	2 years
Expected Start Date	14-Dec-2021
Date Of Approval	14-Dec-2021
Approval Expiry Date	31-Dec-2023
Approved By	Vacancy
Name of Authorised Signatory	Ruth Stirton
Date	14-Dec-2021

*NB. If the actual project start date is delayed beyond 12 months of the expected start date, this Certificate of Approval will lapse and the project will need to be reviewed again to take account of changed circumstances such as legislation, sponsor requirements and University procedures.

Please note and follow the requirements for approved submissions:

Amendments to protocol

- * Any changes or amendments to approved protocols must be submitted to the C-REC for authorisation prior to implementation.

Feedback regarding the status and conduct of approved projects

- * Any incidents with ethical implications that occur during the implementation of the project must be reported immediately to the Chair of the C-REC.

Feedback regarding any adverse(1) and unexpected events(2)

- * Any adverse (undesirable and unintended) and unexpected events that occur during the implementation of the project must be reported to the Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts C-REC. In the event of a serious adverse event, research must be stopped immediately and the Chair alerted within 24 hours of the occurrence.

Monitoring of Approved studies

The University may undertake periodic monitoring of approved studies. Researchers will be requested to report on the outcomes of research activity in relation to approvals that were granted (full applications and amendments).

Research Standards

Failure to conduct University research in alignment with the Code of Practice for Research may be investigated under the Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research or other appropriate internal mechanisms (3). Any queries can be addressed to the Research Governance Office: rgoffice@sussex.ac.uk

(1) An "adverse event" is one that occurs during the course of a research protocol that either causes physical or psychological harm, or increases the risk of physical or psychological harm, or results in a loss of privacy and/or confidentiality to research participant or others.

(2) An "unexpected event" is an occurrence or situation during the course of a research project that was a) harmful to a participant taking part in the research, or b) increased the probability of harm to participants taking part in the research.

(3) <http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/rqi/policy/research-policy>